

D10.4: Communication activities: how to face second half of the project

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Executive summary

This report presents Task by Task (1) the work done within the Work Package 10 of the Valuwaste project (GA 818312) during the first 24 months of the project and (2) the actions planned for the second half of the project. The Work Package 10 Tasks cover:

1. **Task 10.1. Development of a Dissemination & Communication Plan (M1-M3).**
2. **Task 10.2: Educational campaign in Murcia (M9-M24)**
3. **Task 10.3. Citizens awareness campaign in Murcia and Kalundborg (M18-M37, preparation)**
4. **Task 10.4. Promotion of project results to a targeted audience (M4-M48)**
5. **Task 10.5. Communication (M4-M48).**

The most relevant points regarding the progress of the project during the first 24 months of the project are: **(1)** the WP10 has progressed according to expectations; **(2)** the focus of the actions during the first part of the project was on project communication; **(3)** all the scheduled milestones (MS9) and deliverables (D10.1, D10.2 and D10.3) were achieved on time.

The points above (progress made, focus of the actions taken, and challenges encountered during the first half of the project) have been reviewed to design the actions for the second half of project implementation (M24-M48).

The most relevant points regarding future actions for the project are: **(1)** work on communication will continue -Task 10.5-; **(2)** the Educational Campaign in Murcia (Spain)-Task 10.2- will carry out a final set of actions and finish on January 2021; **(3)** the Awareness Campaign in Murcia (Spain) and Kalundborg (Denmark)-Task 10.3-will start in January 2021; **(4)** the project will work to boost the engagement with policy makers, the participation in trade shows and the publication of articles to promote results -Task 10.4; and **(5)** the final event of the project will take place.

1 Introduction

This document gathers and describes the main Valuwaste Project activities regarding dissemination and communication within the first half of project execution and presents the communication actions and strategy for the second half of project development. **The content is structured Task by Task, so it is possible to see the progress made in a WP Task and then the planning for the months ahead for said Task.**

Innovarum (the commercial brand of EURIZON S.L., Partner 2) is the Work Package 10 leader (Dissemination and Communication activities). Innovarum elaborated the Valuwaste Project Communication and Dissemination Plan (D10.1), the review of the actions after 1 year of project development (D10.2: Communication activities: first year of VALUEWASTE project) and oversees the coordination of the different actions that are included in it.

1.1 Tasks inside the WP10

WP 10 consists of the following Tasks:

- **Task 10.1. Development of a Dissemination & Communication Plan (M1-M3)**-Completed
- **Task 10.2: Educational campaign in Murcia (M9-M24)**- In progress, extended to January 2021, see below for more information.
- **Task 10.3. Citizens awareness campaign in Murcia and Kalundborg (M18-M37, preparation)**- In progress
- **Task 10.4. Promotion of project results to a targeted audience (M4-M48)**- In progress
- **Task 10.5. Communication (M4-M48)**-In progress

2 Task 10.1. Development of a Dissemination & Communication Plan

2.1 Basic information

- **Responsible partner:** Innovarum, Communication Coordinator.
- **Status:** M1-M3, finished.

2.2 Progress

The Dissemination & Communication Plan was finished by M3 of the Project (**D10.1**) and covers all tasks and actions included in the WP (T10.2, T10.3, 10.4 and T10.5). The plan counts with a live document¹ meant to track all the communication actions throughout the project. The plan was reviewed in the D10.2.

2.3 Planning for the second half of the project

The live document (excel file) of the D&C Plan will keep on being updated as the project archives new actions. Additionally, the plan will be reviewed on the Deliverable 10.4 *Communication activities: how to face second half of the project*.

¹ An excel file designed to track the progress of the different KPIs month by month.

3 Task 10.2: Educational campaign in Murcia

3.1 Basic information

- **Responsible partner:** MU-FERROVIAL.
- **Status:** M9-M24, in progress.
- **Related milestone:** MS9 - *Launching of the campaign for urban biowaste collection in Murcia.*
- **General actions included:** campaign visual identity, online information, creation of the Organic Biowaste Patrols, visits to target audiences, Information letters, Communication Mass Media, neighbourhood's meetings, an Online survey pre and post biowaste collection, the Organic Collection Kit and education activities.

3.2 Progress

The **Educational Communication Campaign (Task 10.2)** was successfully launched the 10th of November of 2019 by the Murcia City Council and Ferrovial (MS9). From then onwards, both partners coordinated a series of communication actions:

3.2.1 Goal and actions carried out

The goal of the campaign is to ***improve the perception of citizens on urban biowaste as a local source and their enhanced active participation in its separate collection through social innovation initiatives.*** Main actions carried out so far (as described in the GA) are:

1. The creation of the Organic Biowaste Patrols.
2. The creation of a visual identity, dissemination materials and an online strategy that includes the development of a webpage and social media.
3. The delivery of information letter to the citizens of “La Flota” from the Murcia City Council
4. The recording of radio slots.
5. The organisation of meetings with neighbours.
6. The organisation of open talks in schools.
7. On 28th of February of 2020 the selective collection of biowaste started with the allocation of 28 new containers in various locations of the “La Flota” Neighbourhood (Milestone WP1). This action was supported and coordinated with the campaign.
8. Currently, there are 37 containers set: 29 located in La Flota Neighbourhood, 7 in food markets and one in the San Pedro square for nearby restaurants.
9. The launching of one of the online surveys (Target in the Grant Agreement: 1000). By the end of October of 2020, **2,200 surveys** had been carried out in the neighbourhood of “La Flota”. The survey is still running.

It is possible to view the progress of the campaign, relevant updates, and information at the Valuwaste webpage: <http://valuwaste.eu/communication-campaigns/> or at the specific webpage for the Campaign (in Spanish): <http://valuwaste.murciaciudadesostenible.es/>

3.2.2 Numeric targets

The Campaign targets 8,160 neighbours, 130 restaurants in La Flota neighbourhood and 8 food markets in Murcia. Final numeric goal at the end of the campaign is to impact 50% of citizens,

90% of food markets and 70% of restaurants. In October 2020, the situation regarding the target impact numbers of the campaign was:

- 1) 6,420 citizens of La Flota reached, mainly through surveys and the organic biowaste patrols. That is the 80% of the total 8.160 citizens, 30% more than expected.
- 2) 7 markets (75% of the total) reached through direct contact or the organic biowaste patrols. However, engagement with the campaign was low until September 2020.
- 3) 21 restaurants (15% of the total) were contacted. Due to the COVID19, many restaurants had to close or significantly reduce their activity. Thus, their participation in the campaign was almost non-existing.

3.2.3 Deviations: COVID19

Due to the **COVID19 outbreak**, the campaign had to pause offline activities (meetings, promotion in person...) on the 3rd of April of 2020 (M18). This affected particularly the impact over restaurants and markets. However, during that time there was a special emphasis on the social media channels (@MuCSostenible) on the relevance of separating biowaste while at home.

On the 16th of September, the Organic Biowaste Patrols resumed their normal promotion activities, and the Educational Campaign Promotional Trailer was out again on the streets in La Flota Neighbourhood raising awareness. That same month (September 2020, M23), the Murcia Municipality issued a **press release**² announcing the resume of activities of the Campaign and a **mailing campaign to the La Flota neighbours** (Available at the Annexes: *Picture 15: Mailing Campaign from the Educational Campaign in Murcia in September 2020 to re-engage citizens in La Flota Neighbourhood*), explaining the relevance of their participation and boosting their engagement in the coming months.

3.3 Planning for the second half of the project

The first action that will affect the communication strategy of the project in its second half of progress is the extension of the Educational Campaign (Task 10.2). **It was decided in September 2020 that, in order to maximise impact of the Campaign after the pause due to the COVID19 offline activities, the Educational Campaign in Murcia was to be extended until January 2021 (M27).**

3.3.1 Updated version of the Communication Campaign

In September 2020 (M23), a review and **update of the Communication Campaign** with the data gathered from the previous months of the participation of the population and the volume of biowaste collected was carried out. The goal of this update was to increase **the citizens and public markets awareness** about the selective collection, making them part of its progress.

This new updated campaign has new messages, visual content and actions planned until January 2021. These include the following:

² Available at:

<https://centromedios.murcia.es/PUBLICO/NotaPrensa/Default.aspx?pldPagina=25&pldNoticia=57586#ad-image-0>

3.3.1.1 Biowaste patrols

Increase in the number of **members of the biowaste patrol** to reach more citizens. Originally, the patrol counted with 4 to 6 members and with the new additions the patrol would count with 6 to 8 members. Depending on the activity more members would be active to support promotion.

Picture 1: Organic Biowaste patrols on the streets (September-October 2020)

3.3.1.2 Promotional materials and messages

The design and set up of new **promotional banners** and posters close to the Murcia City Council, the Murcia Bus Station, and the Sports Centre.

The **message** for the promotion is: “La Flota (Murcia) needs more, we need your contribution!”

Picture 2: new promotion material of the updated campaign (to be used until January 2021)

Picture 3: promotional materials installed close to the Murcia Bus Station

3.3.1.3 Food markets

Actions regarding food markets include:

(1) Boost local **Food Markets** engagement through the Organic Biowaste Patrols. Design specific **dissemination materials for the Food Market vendors**.

Picture 4: launching of promotion activities in local food markets (17/11/2020). The launching activity counted with support from authorities from the current local government.

(2) Evaluate if it is possible to actively target **Weekly Markets** (which might change locations week to week) in Murcia, in addition to the local food markets. Generate engagement with the Campaign through the Organic Biowaste Patrols and direct contact with the organisers.

3.3.1.4 Online actions

The campaign will evaluate how to better support engagement through online Campaigns and actions (Social media, webpage content...) and evaluate the use of a **Social Media Add Campaign** to increase the impact of the online messages

Picture 5: example of social media promotion (September 2019, Twitter)

3.3.1.5 Support from the Murcia City Council.

Technicians from Murcia City Council will actively participate in the actions targeted to the Food Markets, supporting its engagement in the selective collection and the implementation of the Communication Campaign 1 (Task 10.2)

4 Task 10.3. Citizens awareness campaign in Murcia and Kalundborg

4.1 Basic information

- **Responsible partners:** *Kalundborg Kommune and Ayuntamiento de Murcia* (Kalundborg Municipality and Murcia City Council).
- **Status:** M18-M37.
- **Related milestone:** MS10 - *Launching of the citizens awareness campaign in Murcia and Kalundborg.*
- **General actions included:** advertising initiatives across both municipalities, a cooking workshop on insect-derived products, open visiting arrangements for citizens, an exchange trip between Murcia and Kalundborg and information activities targeting specific audiences.

4.2 Progress

The second Communication Campaign (Task 10.3) is focused on promoting products generated from biowaste and on communicating its applications in real life to citizens in Murcia and Kalundborg. Murcia City Council (P5MURCIA, responsible partner) started preparations on May 2020 (M18). Due to the COVID19 and the change of schedule of the First Communication Campaign (Task 10.2), **activities belonging to the second Communication campaign are expected to start on January 2021 (M27)**, continuing the First Communication Campaign.

4.2.1 Target audiences

Main target audiences of the campaign in both municipalities are:

1. **Children** and students from local educational centres.
2. **Citizens:** which can be reached through neighbourhood associations, municipal bodies civil servants or other local civil associations.

4.2.2 Awareness Campaign in Murcia

In September 2020 and after various meetings with the project coordinator (CETENMA) and the Communication partner (Innovarum), the Murcia City Council finished the **concept and visual identity design of the new Communication Campaign (Task 10.3)**. This new campaign has new messages, new content and new visual elements that are built upon the materials developed for the first Campaign of the project (Task 10.2 Educational Campaign in Murcia). A continuation in the visual line of the Campaign helps the target audiences follow the transition and better understand the new messages.

4.2.2.1 Concept and visual identity of the Campaign in Murcia

The main message of the Awareness Campaign works around the message and invitation “Be part of the cycle”. The Campaign works with the concepts previously explained by the first Campaign of the project (Task 10.2) and works now to invite citizens to not only collect and separate the biowaste, but to understand the potential of the products developed thanks to this new business model.

From “Add one” and “Add more” - Core messages of the first communication campaigns (Task 10.2- this campaign evolves now to “Add to the cycle”, providing further insights on the benefits of circular economy and on the long term benefits of the participation of the population.

Below it is possible to see the main visual elements of the Campaign that will be used in Murcia:

Picture 6: visual elements of the Awareness Campaign of the Valuewaste Project (Task 10.3)

4.2.3 Awareness Campaign in Kalundborg

The Awareness Campaign in Kalundborg is also having to consider restrictions and limitations due to the COVID19. In October 2020, the Murcia City Council, the Kalundborg City Council and Innovarum (Communication partner) met to discuss ideas and to coordinate the work ahead. To keep all parties updated, a second meeting was agreed to take place in December to exchange information and comment on the launching of the activities.

4.3 Planning for the second half of the project

Both Campaigns (Murcia and Kalundborg) are still in a preparatory phase, ideas are being exchanged and information is still being updated. That said, the project partners in charge have already provided a draft plan of the planning of activities.

4.3.1 Ideas to overcome COVID19 restrictions and person to person contact

In the first place, responsible partners have analysed the main activities included in the campaign to identify the ones that could be potentially hampered by COVID19 restrictions. **Activities with the highest risk of being impacted by the COVID (person to person contact) are the cooking workshop, the open visiting arrangements, the exchange trip between Murcia and Kalundborg and potentially the information activities.** Some alternative options to overcome this challenge include:

1. **Use of the digital channels-broadcasting of the cooking workshop:** the Murcia City Council is evaluating transforming the workshop in a broadcasted TV show in a local TV channel.

This option could help assure that target audiences are highly impacted in a COVID safe framework. The Kalundborg City council is evaluating this option as well.

2. **Materials that can be taken home-Information activities targeting specific audiences:** Kalundborg City council is evaluating the creation of specific educational materials for schools and a book for children.
3. **Other activities that require travel or people to people contact like** the open visiting arrangements or the exchange trip between Murcia and Kalundborg: these activities will be scheduled in 2022 to try to avoid COVID19 impact.

4.3.2 Planning and KPIs

On the second place, the numeric indicators and general draft plan for implementation of the actions in both municipalities has been drafted:

Table 1: Awareness Campaign KPIs

Task 10.3 action	KPI	Type of target
Advertising initiatives: billboards and advertising material	15 materials	Internal, reference
Cooking workshop on insect-derived products	2	Mandatory (GA)
Open visiting arrangements for citizens	3 open days- 10 to 20 citizens	Mandatory (GA)
Exchange trips between Murcia and Kalundborg	2 trips - 10 to 15 delegates	Mandatory (GA)
Information activities targeting specific audiences: educational activities	6	Internal, reference
Information activities targeting specific audiences: trainings to municipal body servants	2	Internal, reference
Information activities targeting specific audiences: info-points	4	Internal, reference

Then, the draft planning for activities covers the actions included in Table 2 and Table 3 that can be found in the next page. Before getting to them, some relevant general comments are:

1. The actions included are part of an initial drafted plan. Thus, updates and changes can happen, especially in relation with the development of the COVID19.
2. Actions for 2021 pay special attention to videos and online dissemination channels like broadcasted activities.
3. Onsite visits and activities that require person to person contact have been scheduled for 2022. However, the potential impact of COVID19 over these actions is still deemed high, restrictions could still force the cancellation of the activities.

Table 2: VW Awareness Campaign, drafted plan for 2021

Quarter	Location	Target audience	Generic action block (GA)	Action detail	Potential COVID19 impact
1	Kalundborg	Citizens	Advertising initiatives	Launching info about Valuewaste on SoMe-Small videos on sorting waste	Low
1	Kalundborg	Kindergarden/schools	Information activities targeting specific audiences: educational activities	Education materials, planning and preparation. Finding external author.	Low
1	Murcia	Citizens	Advertising initiatives	Launching of advertising materials promotion on the streets	Low
2	Murcia	Citizens	Information activities targeting specific audiences: trainings to municipal body servants	To be decided	Low
2	Kalundborg	Citizens	Information activities targeting specific audiences: trainings to municipal body servants	To be decided	Low
2	Kalundborg	Citizens	Advertising initiatives	Small videos about waste valorisation	Low
2	Kalundborg	Kindergarden/schools	Information activities targeting specific audiences: educational activities	Preparation of a children's book and other teaching materials	Low
3	Murcia	Kindergarden/schools	Information activities targeting specific audiences: educational activities	To be decided	Medium
3	Murcia	Citizens	Information activities targeting specific audiences: info-points	To be decided, following the launching of advertising materials	Medium
3	Kalundborg	Citizens	Advertising initiatives	Small videos and articles about waste valorisation	Low
3	Kalundborg	Kindergarden/schools	Information activities targeting specific audiences: educational activities	From waste to new resources: introduction of materials to Kindergartens and schools	Medium
3	Murcia	Citizens	Cooking workshop	Live broadcasted cooking workshop about insect protein in local TV	Low
3	Kalundborg	Citizens	Information activities targeting specific audiences: info-points	To be decided	Medium
4	Kalundborg	Citizens	Cooking workshop	Possible workshop on insect protein and food - likely virtual	Low

Quarter	Location	Target audience	Generic action block (GA)	Action detail	Potential COVID19 impact
4	Kalundborg	Kindergarden/schools	Information activities targeting specific audiences: educational activities	Support to schools who want to engage and activities about sorting waste and waste valorisation. Biowaste as a source of resources.	Medium

Table 3: VW Awareness Campaign, drafted plan for 2022

Quarter	Location	Target audience	Generic action block (GA)	Action detail	Potential COVID19 impact
1	Murcia & Kalundborg	Citizens	Exchange trip between Murcia and Kalundborg	Delegates come from Murcia to see waste valorisation work and production of BIO protein.	High
1	Kalundborg	Citizens	Open visiting arrangements for citizens	Arrangement on UNIBIO where citizens can see their facilities and learn about it.	Medium
1	Kalundborg	Kindergarden/schools	Information activities targeting specific audiences: educational activities-Cooking workshop	Inviting a Danish Chef specialised in cooking with insects and arrange visits to schools to do a demonstration/cooking show.	Medium
1	Murcia	Citizens	Open visiting arrangements for citizens	To be decided: citizens visits to the waste treatment plant in Cañada Hermosa	Medium
1	Murcia & Kalundborg	Citizens	Exchange trip between Murcia and Kalundborg	To be decided: delegates come from Kalundborg to see the waste treatment plant in Cañada Hermosa (Murcia)	High
2	Murcia & Kalundborg	Citizens	Follow up	Follow up, evaluation	Low
2	Murcia & Kalundborg	Kindergarden/schools	Follow up	Follow up, evaluation	Low

5 Task 10.4. Promotion of project results to a targeted audience

5.1 Basic information

- **Responsible partner:** Innovarum, Communication Coordinator.
- **Status:** M4-M48, ongoing.
- **General actions included:** presence in key technical sector events (fairs and trade shows), technical publications, and attendance to high level policy events.

5.2 Progress

The ValueWaste Project has engaged in several actions such as trade shows, fairs, high level policy events or technical publications as reported above. That said, since the project is starting now to produce results, most opportunities related to these actions have been used for the general communication of the project.

Table 4: Task 10.4 targets and progress overview

Action No.	Action name	Target	Lead	M24	Strategy	Target Audience
4A	Trade shows and fairs	15 events attended	Innovarum	7	Communication Dissemination	4 - Industry players
5A	Technical publications/ Papers	5 publications	Innovarum	5	Dissemination	5 - Academia
3A	Meetings with policy makers	5 meetings	MURCIA	10	Dissemination	3 - Policy makers
3B	Attendance to high level policy events	5 events	CETENMA, MURCIA, Kalundborg	2	Dissemination	3 - Policy makers

5.2.1 Trade shows and fairs

5.2.1.1 Quality of the actions

The trade shows in which the project partners participated were relevant for the project and counted with a high volume of attendees, most of them representants of the industry circles. The topic of the attended events included waste valorisation, smart cities, or waste management.

However, in general, the COVID 19 situation has complicated the participation in events with “trade show” format throughout 2020. After a pause in the organisation of these types of events, it has been possible to see that some of them are now being readapted: online booths and other innovative tools are appearing. For example, in June 2020 EUBIA participated in the EUBCE 2020 online edition with a digital project booth in which it promoted the ValueWaste project.

Picture 7: EUBIA's eBooth at EUBCE 2020

Another perceived change in the situation is that some events that originally had a more classic “trade show” structure are becoming matchmaking or more conference like events when they are adapted to an “online” version.

5.2.1.2 Numeric progress

Below are the trade show or fair events with participation of the Valuwaste project:

Table 5: Trade shows and fairs with participation of the Valuwaste project. Main target audience: industry.

Date	Title	Partner	Description	Attendees	Link
26/09/2019	EXPOBIOMAS A 2019 Valladolid	Inderen	Oral presentation of the project and distribution of the RETENMA magazine and the Valuwaste article	16,540 attendees and 540 exhibitors	https://www.expobiomas.com/info-practica
02/10/2019	Ecofira 2019	Ferrovial	Company booth, Valuwaste roll up and brochures.	103 exhibitors	http://ecofira.feriavalencia.com/en/ecofira-feria-internacional-de-las-soluciones-medioambientales/
08/11/2019	Activity in the Murcia Science Week- <i>Semana de la Ciencia y la Tecnología de Murcia</i>	CETENMA, Ferrovial, ENTOMO	Project booth with information and interactive activities	40,000 attendees for the whole event - around 1500 visitors to the stand	http://fseneca.es/secyt19/
01/02/2020	MESSE I KALUNDBORG 2020	Kalundborg	Company booth with informative materials of the Valuwaste project: poster and Roll-up	1,543 attendees	https://www.kalundborgerhverv.dk/messe-i-kalundborg-i-2020/

06/06/2020	EUBCE 2020 online	EUBIA	Company booth with Valuewaste dissemination content.	"1,551 participants from 87 countries	https://www.eubia.org/cms/2020/07/14/eubias-highlights-from-the-28th-eubce/
02/10/2020	EUROCITIES Horizon 2020 Green Deal calls online brokerage event	MURCIA	Brief presentation of VW as a good practice, to promote circular economy projects for the new call of H2020.	5,180 visitors, 1,538 attendees to the Monday opening session"	https://h2020-green-deal-call-dublin.b2match.io/
05/10/2020	Activity in the Madrid Science and Innovation Week	Innovarum	Online interactive activity	31 registrations	https://www.semanacienciaMadrid.org/actividad/como-transformar-residuos-organicos-en-recursos-valiosos-en-tu-ciudad

5.2.2 Technical publications

5.2.2.1 Quality of the actions

Technical publications are reviewed before being published, assuring content quality and adequacy.³ So far, technical publications include 4 articles in magazines targeted to a technical audience and 1 paper.

The technical magazines where the project was published are popular media channels of interest for academia and industry audiences with a high volume of readers. On the one hand, the project has made publications in the “**Retema Magazine**” a technical publication specialised in the environment distributed through public administration offices, Universities and Research Centres. Approximately, the publication counts with 18,000 readers, most of them coming from Spain and Europe.⁴

On the other hand, the project has also published in the bilingual technical magazine “**FuturENVIRO**”. The magazine is mainly distributed in Spain (50%) Europe (20%) and Latin America (20%) to International, European, Spanish, Regional and Local Public Bodies & Institutions, Environmental Project Developers and Universities, R&D Centres and Technological Institutes (among others).⁵ Together with its online edition, this magazine reaches out globally to over 110,000 professionals.

³ Clarification on **what a “technical publication” covers**: As indicated in the GA and in the D10.1, this action covers: (1) the publication of the relevant results in the evolution of the VALUEWASTE project in specialised national and international magazines on waste, urban waste, waste management, recycling, reusing, circular economy or bio-economy; and (2) the publication of papers

⁴ Retema media kit:

<https://www.retema.es/require/archivos/publicidad/KzMg7M1XM8k27T9K1mNwYNVR9FkQnbbbo8.pdf>

⁵ Future Enviro media Kit: https://futurenviro.es/wp-content/uploads/2020/05/TarifasFuturENVIRO_2020.pdf

Finally, the paper publication that the project has published for now belongs to **the ISPIM virtual innovation conference “Innovating in times of crisis”**, a renowned event among the academia circles.

5.2.2.2 *Numeric progress*

This section presents the technical publications (accorded to the description in the Work Package 10) of the project:

Table 6: Technical publications produced by the Valuewaste project

Date	Title	Who	Link
18/12/2018	Kokonaisratkaisui bioarvoketjun hyödyntämiseksi	Article	https://juuli.fi/Search/Results?lookfor=Kokonaisratkaisui+bioarvoketjun+hy%C3%B6dynt%C3%A4miseksi&type=AllFields
11/09/2019	Revista Retema- VALUEWASTE convertirá residuos urbanos en comida	Article in magazine	https://www.retema.es/revistas/julio-agosto-Lp5F1
29/09/2019	Especial Bioenergía- Valorización integral de biorresiduos en el marco del proyecto ValueWaste	Article in magazine	https://www.retema.es/revistas/especial-bioenergia-jLyeG
10/06/2020	ISPIM virtual innovation conference “Innovating in times of crisis”	Paper	https://www.ispim-innovation.com/post/call-for-submissions-ispim-innovation-conference-berlin
28/06/2020	Future enviro- DOES THE CIRCULAR ECONOMY DISTINGUISH BETWEEN GENDERS?	Article in magazine	https://futureenviro.es/digital-versions/2020-05/index.html

Picture 8: technical publications of the VW project

5.2.3 High level policy events

5.2.3.1 Quality of the actions

High level policy events have been reviewed in this Deliverable to assure the relevance of the actions included. Thus, D10.4 does not include “Coordinators Days” as high-level policy events (present in D10.1 and D10.2). They were taken out of the list after throughout review of the content.

5.2.3.2 Numeric progress

Table 7 shows the high-level policy events in which Valuwaste has been represented:

Table 7: Representation of Valuwaste in High level policy events

Date	Title	Who	Link	Goal & Participation
22/11/2018	Experts Workshop on Urban Circular Bioeconomy,	CETENMA	https://www.resurbis.eu/EU-workshop-on-circular-economy	General goal of the event: collect inputs on how to draft, finance, implement and assess an urban circular bioeconomy strategy. Participation: debate and introduction of the Valuwaste project.
06/12/2018	Meeting of the EU Platform on Food Losses and Food Waste	CETENMA	https://ec.europa.eu/food/safety/food_waste/eu_actions/eu-platform_en	General goal of the event: identify, measure, understand and find solutions to deal with food waste. Participation: participation, Valuwaste project slides included in the presentation delivered by Karen FABBRI, Head of Sector (DG RTD F3): “FOOD 2030: A Policy Framework to Future-Proof our Food Systems”

Meetings with policy makers

5.2.3.3 Quality of the actions

In general, meetings with policy makers have been used so far as a communication tool of the project. Mainly, local policy makers from Murcia or Kalundborg have been introduced to the project goals and characteristics. Meetings have been carried out within the context of a bigger event or as specific scheduled actions. Encountered policy makers have been interested in the project and in general wanted to see how its implementation was going to be done.

5.2.3.4 Numeric progress

Table 8 shows the meetings with policy makers and the feedback provided by them.

Table 8: meetings with policy makers of the Valuewaste project partners

Date	Title	Partner	Links	Feedback
23/11/2018	Promoting ValueWaste with the company. Distribution of informative brochures about the value waste- Presentación Plan Mitigación Cambio Climático Ayuntamiento de Murcia	Ayuntamiento de Murcia	https://www.laverdad.es/murcia/ciudad-murcia/murcia-dota-estrategia-20190318005012-ntvo.html	People were surprised by the characteristics and goals of the project but interested. They had questions on the steps the project would follow. Policy makers had questions on the project and doubts on the safety of the final product for human consumption. They also had inquiries about the legal procedures to bring the product to the market.
26/11/2018	Presentation of the VW project during the visit of the government of Murcia Region (including its president and employment/environment Counselor) and companies to CETENMA	CETENMA	https://twitter.com/CETENMA/status/1067071651383296001	Local government from Murcia expressed support to the project. The local government has defined a Circular Economy strategy and is working to create a specific plan for the Murcia city. Policy makers showed interest in the biowaste selective collection process, many municipalities will join the initiative in the future and will need advice from the project. Policy makers also congratulated the work of CETENMA and Entomo Agroindustrial as relevant companies that support the sustainable development of the city of Murcia.
18/12/2018	Presentation and meeting with The Danish Agriculture & Food Council	ABP		Representants from the Danish Agriculture & Food Council listened to the presentation of the project and had questions on food safety and legal procedures.
13/02/2019	The Murcia City Council visits Cañada Hermosa	Ay. Murcia	Files	The mayor of the Murcia Municipality visited the facilities of the Valuewaste project in Cañada Hermosa. He showed support for the project and interest in its development.

Date	Title	Partner	Links	Feedback
22/08/2019	Visiting center - Trelleborg Municipality, Sweden	Kalundborg Kommune		Representants from the Trelleborg Municipality wanted to know more about the project and about Kalundborg experience with organic waste management. They expressed general interest and curiosity about the project.
29/08/2019	The Trade Council from the Danish Ministry of Foreign Affairs - The Danish Trade Office in Barcelona	ABP)	http://spanien.um.dk/da/eksportraadet/spanien-som-marketed/messer%20og%20eksportfremstoed/	Policy makers in the meeting were interested in the development of the project so far and had questions about the pilot cities of the project (Murcia and Kalundborg).
18/12/2019	Meeting with CESPAs and the Murcia City Hall	Ay. Murcia		Meeting between CESPAs MU FERROVIAL and representants from the Municipality of Murcia. Reviewed the project and expressed interest in its progress.
31/01/2020	Meeting with the Counselor of Industry (Murcia region) in a visit to CETENMA	CETENMA	https://www.cetenma.es/la-consejera-ana-martinez-vidal-visita-cetenma-para-conocer-nuestros-desarrollos-tecnologicos/	Presentation of the project to the Counsellor of Industry (Murcia region) in a visit to CETENMA. The counsellor was interested and gave positive feedback on the progress so far.
12/03/2020	Meeting with the Director of the Development Institute and Innovation responsible (Government of the Region of Murcia), Directors and Presidents of the Technology Centres of the Region of Murcia.	CETENMA		Presentation of the new VW video (Assistants: Director of the Development Institute and Innovation responsible (Government of the Region of Murcia), Directors and Presidents of the Technology Centres of the Region of Murcia)
28/05/2020	1st Pohjois - Savon ilmastofoorumi-Participation virtually to the first North-Savo climate forum meeting /Tuomo Eskelinen	Savonia Univertisy	https://hiilineutraalipohjoissavo.fi/ilmastotyoy/ilmastofoorumi/	Tuomo Eskelinen received positive feedback from the policy makers on the project.

Date	Title	Partner	Links	Feedback
12/08/2020	Ilmastotreffit. In a meeting with regional authorities Valuwaste was presented as a project which have positive effect on climate	Savonia Univertisy		Tuomo Eskelinen received positive feedback from the policy makers on the project.
27/08/2020	2nd Pohjois -Savon ilmastofoorumi-Participation virtually to the second meeting of North-Savo climate forum /Tuomo Eskelinen	Savonia Univertisy	https://hiilineutraalipohjoissavo.fi/pohjois-savon-ilmastofoorumin-materiaalit-27-8-2020/	Tuomo Eskelinen received positive feedback from the policy makers on the project.

5.3 Planning for the second half of the project

The work of the “dissemination of results” Task (Task 10.4) will increase from M24 onwards. This goes in line with the project plan, which expects to produce most of results for the second half of the project and towards the end.

5.3.1 Trade shows

It will be a goal of the communication and dissemination of the second half of the project to increase the participation in trade shows. For this reason, Innovarum will track project partner actions and encourage them to keep up the active dissemination of the project. Additionally, to achieve this goal, Innovarum will:

1. Elaborate an updated list with trades shows/events of interest for the project (attached in Annexes).
2. Send this reference list to the project consortium to ask for suggestions or ideas.
3. Ask project partners to review the commonly created list for trade shows and identify options that are suitable for them and for the promotion of the project.

An example of a relevant recommended trade show is **the Sustainable Environmental Solutions Forum (FSMS) 2021**, a global gathering event that places value on advances in environmental sustainability. Held every two years in Madrid (ES), the FSMS has become an umbrella for more than a dozen events, conferences, trade shows and congresses. Next event is due for June 2021.

5.3.1.1 Own organised events

Innovarum (Communication partner) will organise together with the Project Coordinator (CETENMA) an interactive online workshop targeted to industry stakeholders to promote project results. The specific topic of this online activity is still to be defined; however, the initial idea is to invite members of the Executive Advisory Board to contribute with their expertise.

5.3.2 Technical publications

Even though the current target set for “Technical publications” is complete, project partners will also be encouraged to keep on publishing on their progress. In this regard, Innovarum (Communication Partner) will:

1. Elaborate an updated list with relevant technical publications (including not only papers by technical magazines in general, as it is described in the GA) during January 2021.
2. Send this reference lists the project consortium to ask for suggestions or ideas.
3. Ask project partners in which publications they would be able to publish and an indicative timing for publications.

Innovarum will also remind all partners of the obligation to disseminate results included in the GA, which is summarised in point 8.2 (Obligation to Disseminate Results).

5.3.2.1 Peer reviewed publications

The project will keep on looking for opportunities to do peer-reviewed publications. Nonetheless, it will also be important to keep on paying attention to the correct use of all related IPR, common in an innovation project as Valuewaste.

5.3.3 High level policy events & meetings with policy makers

The communication and dissemination of the project will align with the points and ideas established in D9.4 *Valuewaste influence on EU policy regarding biowaste management and valorisation*. This deliverable takes a look at the EU legislative framework impacting the biowaste valorisation pathways promoted by the ValueWaste project and presents strategies to get the Policy makers to know and understand the opportunities made available by projects and results such as Valuewaste.

One key point is the identification of key actions that could influence the course of EU policy making:

1. Contact with EU Commission before the publication of a relevant legislative proposal.
2. Contact when the legislative proposal is analysed by the EU Parliament (during legislative process)
3. Contact with European Food and Safety Authority (EFSA) officials and Policy Officers of the EU Commission -at any moment.

Then, identified options to carry out meetings with representants from the groups above include:

1. Appointment request (usually harder to achieve for the EU Commission than for the EU Parliament)
2. Invitation to own organised events/workshops (usually doable)
3. Meeting during third party events/workshops organized in Brussels (easy)
4. Meeting/Chat during public events organized in the EU Parliament (easy)
5. Chat prior/during/after Parliamentary committee meetings (easy)

Finally, the table below shows a drafted schedule of the actions to carry these contacts out:

Table 9: D9.4 roadmap of policy actions

Date	Action point
November 2020 - February 2021	General brainstorming. Design of common key messages
March-April 2021	Press releases with key messages. Lobbying actions.
May-July 2021	Organisation of 2 interactive webinars. Attendance of EU officials previously contacted and efforts to obtain audit or an initial discussion from EFSA.
September-December 2021	Participation in an event/workshop in Brussels. Evaluation of the organisation of additional webinars
January-March 2022	Lobbying actions. Publication of a final set of policy recommendations signed by Scalibur, Valuewaste and Hoop.
April-June 2022	Organization of a final public event, possibly in the Committee of the European Parliament dealing with Environmental legislation (ENVI).

It is important to note that, until the second half of 2021 the project does not expect to organise any physical venue/meeting due to the COVID19 situation.

5.3.3.1 Collaboration with other projects

VW will seek the cooperation with other EU funded projects focussing on circular economy. Namely, these projects are Scalibur, WaysTUP and Hoop, with whom the project is already engaging in active cooperation and communication actions support.

Next meeting with these projects (for the general brainstorming and design of common key messages) will take place the 10th of December of 2020.

5.3.3.2 The new EU Circular Cities and Regions Initiative (CCRI)

The CCRI aims to support the implementation of circular economy solutions at local and regional scale. Valuwaste will also contribute to the activities and actions carried out by the CCRI through the HOOP project, coordinated by CETENMA.⁶

More information on the development of these actions targeted to policy makers can be found in D9.4.

5.3.4 Launch of the Pilot Plant in Murcia: results dissemination

The launching of the Valuwaste Pilot plant in Cañada Hermosa (Murcia, Spain) in November is a key step in the development of the project. Dissemination related to the work in the Plant is expected, actions related to the Task 10.4 (results dissemination) will support and increase awareness about it.

In this regard, CETENMA (project coordinator) is already evaluating the organisation of a “Launching event” where policy makers and other relevant parties would be invited.

Besides, other dissemination actions can include the publication of updated articles in technical magazines or papers on specific results.

⁶ ValueWaste is one of the mother projects of HOOP which has been selected as one of the projects contributing to the implementation of the CCRI.

6 Task 10.5. Communication

6.1 Basic information

- **Responsible partner:** Innovarum, Communication Coordinator
- **Status:** M4-M48, ongoing.
- **General actions included:** the project website, engagement with project partner's websites, on-line social networks, audio-visual material, attendance to conferences, press releases, meetings with policy makers and final event.

6.2 Progress

In general, communication actions show good numerical and qualitative results. Below there are some comments regarding the quality and quantity of the actions:

Table 10: Task 10.5 targets and progress overview

Action No.	Action name	Target	Lead	M24	Strategy	Target Audience
1A	VALUEWASTE website & Blog	500 visits/month	Innovarum	650	Communication Dissemination	1 - All target audiences
1A	Publications in blog	30 posts	Innovarum	30	Communication	1 - All target audiences
1B	Social Media Twitter	300 followers	Innovarum	352	Communication	1 - All target audiences
1B	Social Media LinkedIn	100 followers	Innovarum	298	Communication	1 - All target audiences
1C	Audio-visual materials	2 videos	Innovarum	2	Communication	1 - All target audiences
1D	Other informative materials	15 informative materials	Innovarum	12	Communication	1 - All target audiences
1E	Media coverage (included press releases)	100 media coverages	All partners	91	Communication	1 - All target audiences
1F	Final event	80-100 attendees	Cetenma	Project end	Communication Dissemination	1 - All target audiences
1G	EC Dissemination routes	Presence in 4 routes	Innovarum	5	Communication Dissemination	1 - All target audiences
5B	Workshops, conferences, and congresses	10 events	Innovarum	41	Communication Dissemination	5 - Academia

6.2.1 Webpage and social media

6.2.1.1 Quality of the actions

The **webpage** (www.valuewaste.eu) and the **social media accounts** (Twitter and LinkedIn) have supported all communication actions, building a community around the project and engagement with the different audiences.

Social media channels shared tailored content for Twitter and LinkedIn about different topics: the project activity, publications, or content of interest to its audiences, content and updates from other EU H2020 projects...

The **blog** has been active and has shared updates on the project development. It has also created sections and tags, so it is possible to easily group content related to the First Communication Campaign (Task 10.2), to the launching of the Valuwaste Pilot Plant, or to the project general activity. The list of published posts includes:

Table 11: blog posts of the Valuwaste project

Title	Date
ValueWaste Kick-Off meeting	23/04/2019
ValueWaste joins Biorefine Cluster Europe	27/08/2019
Agro Business Park presents Valuwaste to a Chinese Delegation	03/09/2019
ABP meets with The Trade Council from the Danish Ministry of Foreign Affairs	03/09/2019
Food Festival 2019: Northern Europe biggest food event	16/09/2019
Dansk Bioøkonomi Konference 2019	02/10/2019
Valuwaste General Assembly 2019	24/10/2019
CETENMA and Valuwaste at Climathon Murcia 2019	11/11/2019
Ecofira 2019 & “Foro Comprometidos”	11/11/2019
MurciaSumaUno: the Murcia Communication Campaign	16/12/2019
Business Models: Entomo and Savonia University workshop	19/12/2019
INDEREN successfully delivered 2 digester tanks of 100m ³ and 20m ³	15/01/2020
MurciaSumaUno: The Organic Biowaste Patrols are on the streets	15/01/2020
Valuwaste and the Solar Impulse Label	19/02/2020
Valuwaste has new flyers!	19/02/2020
MurciaSumaUno: Neighbourhood’s meetings, radio slots and information letters	20/02/2020
MurciaSumaUno: the brown organic container is on the streets	05/03/2020
Valuwaste at the Waste Management in the Circular Economy Event	05/03/2020
Valuwaste has a new video presentation!	22/04/2020
New interview with Valuwaste!	20/05/2020
Valuwaste at the eWorkshop on Upcycled Proteins	02/06/2020
Interview with the Organic Biowaste Patrol!	15/06/2020
New section in our webpage: Technical Publications	31/07/2020
Valuwaste Innovation Team meets up	09/09/2020
Meeting of the Valuwaste COVID-19 Committee	15/09/2020
Valuwaste Innovation Team meeting pictures!	21/09/2020
Partners meet up to discuss Pilot Plant Installation procedures	21/09/2020
Shipment of the Pilot Unit to Murcia!	28/09/2020
Installation of the Pilot plant begins!	29/09/2020
Interview with Gemma Castejón from CETENMA	20/10/2020

6.2.1.2 Numeric progress

As a result of the content strategy and all project partners support, both channels have been active and the number of published posts (a total of 30 by M24) and followers in social media (352 in Twitter and 298 in LinkedIn) have steadily increased.

Figure 1: VW webpage views since its opening. www.valuewaste.eu

Webpage views surpassed the 500 per month target on October 2019, 5 months after its launching. It is also possible to see pics of view on January 2020 and September 2020. Likely, this is due to (1) the increase in interest in the project audiences caused by the successful **delivery of the digester tanks in January 2020** and (2) the pick of activity of the project partners and the **innovation team in September 2020**. Both actions were covered in blog and later promoted through project social media channels, which drove visits to the web.

Figure 2: VW Twitter followers' progression. Twitter account: [@ValuewasteP](https://twitter.com/ValuewasteP)

Figure 3: VW LinkedIn followers' progression. LinkedIn account: [Valuewaste H2020 Project](https://www.linkedin.com/company/Valuewaste-H2020-Project)

Both social media channels have surpassed their established numeric target for followers (as in the Grant Agreement).

6.2.2 Audio visual materials and informative materials

6.2.2.1 Quality of the actions

Audio visual materials and **general informative materials** are continuously reviewed and updated, supporting the communication of the project and the communication actions of all project partners. In total, the project has produced a total of 12 informative materials and 2 project videos (informative materials).

6.2.2.2 Numeric progress

Table 12: Audio visual materials produced

Date	Title
28/02/2020	Short video
01/04/2020	Long video (EN/ES) with and without subtitles

Table 13: other informative materials produced

Date	Title
2019	Poster
2019	Roll up
2019	Fact sheet (Technical)
01/02/2019	Valuewaste flyer
01/06/2019	Dissemination KIT
01/07/2019	Process 1 informative factsheet
01/07/2019	Process 2 informative factsheet
01/07/2019	Process 3 informative factsheet
01/09/2019	ValueWaste Basic Presentation
01/09/2019	ValueWaste Slideshow
01/08/2020	Short videos: organic biowaste patrols
01/10/2020	Valuewaste poster IFIB

In regards to these materials, all of them are available at: <http://valuewaste.eu/available-material/>

6.2.3 Media coverages

6.2.3.1 Quality of the actions

The **media coverages** have steadily improved its quality, including publications in various local and national newspapers, radio slots and television interviews.

Picture 9: samples of media coverages of the Valuewaste project

From M1 (November 2018) to M24 (October 2020) the Valuewaste Project has been mentioned in 91 media coverages. The 91 media coverages include 9 press releases, 11 radio mentions and interviews, 2 tv interview, 5 mentions in magazines and 7 in newsletters, 26 mentions in newspapers and 31 articles in relevant webpages. All partners have contributed to this action.

The project 9 press releases cover:

Date	Title	Link
08/10/2018	Press release - Project start	
21/11/2019	Press release - Brown container presentation- Comercio y Limpieza informan a las plazas de abastos sobre la instalación del quinto contenedor de recogida de orgánico	https://centromedios.murcia.es/PUBLICO/NotaPrensa/Default.aspx?pldPagina=25&pldNoticia=54260
10/12/2019	Press release- Selective collection- Murcia, líder europeo en recogida selectiva con la implantación del quinto contenedor	https://centromedios.murcia.es/PUBLICO/NotaPrensa/Default.aspx?pldPagina=25&pldNoticia=54537
09/01/2020	Press release-Murcia Educaitional Campaign- Ayuntamiento de Comienza la fase de información de la campaña 'Suma 1' para dar a conocer a los vecinos de La Flota el nuevo contenedor marrón web page	https://centromedios.murcia.es/PUBLICO/NotaPrensa/Default.aspx?pldPagina=25&pldNoticia=54959
27/02/2020	Press release-Murcia Educaitional Campaign- Ayuntamiento de Murcia -Los vecinos de La Flota estrenarán mañana viernes el nuevo servicio de recogida de residuos orgánicos	https://centromedios.murcia.es/PUBLICO/NotaPrensa/Default.aspx?pldPagina=25&pldNoticia=55663
26/08/2020	Press release -Murcia Educaitional Campaign- Murcia se suma a un proyecto europeo de gestión de los residuos orgánicos y de los procedentes de la construcción	https://centromedios.murcia.es/PUBLICO/NotaPrensa/Default.aspx?pldPagina=25&pldNoticia=57266#ad-image-0
04/09/2020	Press release -Murcia Educaitional Campaign- Murcia liderará un proyecto europeo sobre la puesta en valor de productos derivados del tratamiento de agua y residuos orgánicos urbanos	https://centromedios.murcia.es/PUBLICO/NotaPrensa/Default.aspx?pldPagina=25&pldNoticia=57341#ad-image-0
17/09/2020	Press release -Valuwaste Pilot Plant - West Flemish technology	
26/09/2020	Press release -Murcia Educaitional Campaign- La campaña informativa 'Murcia suma uno' vuelve al barrio de La Flota	https://centromedios.murcia.es/PUBLICO/NotaPrensa/Default.aspx?pldPagina=25&pldNoticia=57586#ad-image-0

6.2.3.2 Numeric progress

Then, the media coverages of the Valuwaste project include:

Table 14: Media Coverage M1-M24

Date	Title	Type	Link
08/10/2018	Press release - Project start	Press release	
08/10/2018	LA VERDAD DE MURCIA - El Contenedor marrón se instala en Murcia	Webpage news	El contenedor marrón se instalará a partir de septiembre en el barrio ...
20/11/2018	VALUEWASTE reúne a 17 socios en torno a la valorización de los residuos orgánicos en Murcia	Webpage news	https://www.retema.es/noticia/valuwaste-reune-a-17-socios-en-torno-a-la-valorizacion-de-los-residuos-organicos-en--KgcPP?platform=hootsuite
20/11/2018	ITAINNOVA participa en el proyecto VALUEWASTE para la recuperación de recursos de los residuos orgánicos generados por ciudadanos	Webpage news	https://empresason.com/art/5286/itainnova-participa-en-el-proyecto-valuewaste-para-la-recuperacion-de-recursos-de-los-residuos-organicos-generados-por-ciudadanos
21/11/2018	La Región lidera un proyecto pionero para transformar los residuos orgánicos en proteínas, piensos y fertilizantes	Newspaper	http://officialpress.es/la-region-dirige-un-proyecto-pionero-para-transformar-los-residuos-organicos-en-proteinas-piensos-y-fertilizantes/

Date	Title	Type	Link
21/11/2018	Página Ayuntamiento de Murcia - Murcia acoge la reunión transnacional destinada a cambiar la gestión de residuos y hallar nuevas formas de alimentación	Webpage news	https://centromedios.murcia.es/PUBLICO/NotaPrensa/Default.aspx?pldPagina=25&pldNoticia=49831
21/11/2018	7TVREGIONDEMURCIA -Murcia probará el contenedor de residuos orgánicos en los barrios que más reciclan	Webpage news	Murcia probará el contenedor de residuos orgánicos en los barrios ...
21/11/2018	VIVA LA RADIO. Murcia y Kalundborg (Dinamarca), lideran experiencia piloto "VALUEWASTE" (residuos valor)	Radio Interview	https://www.orm.es/programas/viva-la-radio-34-valuewaste-34-residuo-valor/
22/11/2018	Ecoticias- Murcia lidera un proyecto pionero para transformar los residuos orgánicos en proteínas, piensos y fertilizantes	Webpage news	https://www.ecoticias.com/residuos-reciclaje/189821/Murcia-lidera-proyecto-pionero-transformar-residuos-organicos#.W_zr_PQwYu0.twitter
22/11/2018	20 MINUTOS - El quinto contenedor se instala en Murcia	Webpage news	El quinto contenedor se instalará a partir de septiembre en el barrio ...
23/11/2018	Innovation Network for Bioresources	Newsletter	Files
23/11/2018	LA SER - Murcia implanta el quinto contenedor	Radio	Murcia implantará en septiembre el quinto contenedor de residuos ...
28/11/2018	La Verdad (Innovation supplement)- Convertir residuos urbanos en comida, una apuesta que contribuye a la economía circular	Article in newspaper	
11/12/2018	INDEREN WEB NEWS- INDEREN is taking part in the VALUEWASTE project	Webpage news	https://inderen.es/eu-funded-project-valuewaste/
11/12/2018	Aragón Radio - interview with Salvador Izquierdo	Radio Interview	
16/12/2018	LA VERDAD DE MURCIA- La planta de Cañada Hermosa tendrá una granja de larvas para producir proteínas	Webpage news	La planta de Cañada Hermosa tendrá una granja de larvas para ...
23/12/2018	ARAGONHOY.NET - ITAINNOVA participa en el proyecto VALUEWASTE para la recuperación de recursos de los residuos orgánicos generados por ciudadanos	Webpage news	http://www.aragonhoy.net/index.php/mod.noticias/mem.detalle/re/menu.46/id.235820
23/12/2018	ELPERIODICODEARAGON.COM - Itainnova participa en la recuperación de recursos de residuos orgánicos	Webpage news	https://www.elperiodicodearagon.com/noticias/aragon/itainnova-participa-recuperacion-recursos-residuos-organicos_1332309.html
26/12/2018	Residuos Profesional- Murcia, campo de pruebas del proyecto europeo de valorización de residuos orgánicos VALUEWASTE	Article in technical journal webpage	https://www.residuosprofesional.com/murcia-proyecto-valuewaste/
26/12/2018	Aragón Radio - interview with Salvador Izquierdo	Radio Interview	http://www.aragonradio.es/podcast/emision/181277/
27/12/2018	Pacto de alcalde Webpage- Proyecto H2020 VALUEWASTE	Webpage news	http://www.pactocaldesregmurcia.es/?q=blog/proyecto-h2020-valuewaste
27/12/2018	Pacto de alcalde Webpage- LA PLANTA DE CAÑADA HERMOSA TENDRÁ UNA GRANJA DE LARVAS PARA PRODUCIR PROTEÍNAS	Webpage news	http://www.pactocaldesregmurcia.es/?q=blog/la-planta-de-ca%C3%B1ada-hermosa-tendr%C3%A1-una-granja-de-larvas-para-producir-prote%C3%Adnas
01/01/2019	Kokonaisratkaisu bioarvoketjun hyödyntämiseksi- SAVONIA UNIVERSITY Magazine	Magazine	https://portal.savonia.fi/amk/fi/tutustu-savoniaan/organisaatio-ia-johtaminen/savonian-viestinta/savonian-sanomat
17/01/2019	Curiosity 7 RM- VALUEWASTE: Un nuevo proyecto europeo en torno a los residuos	TV interview	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=FMNgFz6eKQI
18/01/2019	La Verdad- Una marca de ropa, una plataforma de venta 'online' y un proyecto agrario, premios Emprendedor del Mes	Newspaper	https://www.laverdad.es/murcia/marca-ropa-plataforma-20190118122128-nt.html

Date	Title	Type	Link
19/01/2019	La Verdad- La harina de mosca te hace emprendedor	Newspaper	https://www.laopiniondemurcia.es/comunidad/2019/01/19/harina-mosca-emprendedor/989801.html
17/02/2019	Página Ayuntamiento de Murcia - Murcia participa en un proyecto europeo que permitirá revalorizar 1.800 toneladas de residuos sólidos urbanos y reducir 540 toneladas de CO2 al año	Webpage news	https://www.murcia.com/noticias/2019/02/17-murcia-participa-en-un-proyecto-europeo-que-permitira-revalorizar-1800-toneladas-de-residuos-solidos-urbanos-y-reducir-540-t.asp
04/03/2019	La Verdad- Murcia tendrá la primera granja de larvas de mosca de España	Newspaper	https://www.laopiniondemurcia.es/murcia/2019/03/04/murcia-tendra-primera-granja-larvas/1001732.html
11/03/2019	La Opinión- Se crea en Cehegín un centro para tratar materia orgánica usando insectos	Newspaper	https://www.laopiniondemurcia.es/municipios/2019/03/11/crea-cehegin-centro-investigacion-tratar/1004033.html
12/03/2019	La Verdad-Crean el primer centro investigador para tratar materia orgánica usando insectos	Newspaper	https://www.laverdad.es/murcia/otros-municipios/crean-primer-centro-20190312012418-ntvo.html
02/04/2019	Heraldo de Aragón - Proyecto Europeo sobre residuos tan valiosos que hasta se pueden comer Online	Webpage news	https://www.heraldo.es/noticias/sociedad/2019/04/02/residuos-tan-valiosos-que-se-pueden-comer-1306870.html
02/04/2019	Heraldo de Aragón - Proyecto Europeo sobre residuos tan valiosos que hasta se pueden comer Paper	Magazine	
03/04/2019	Cadena Ser - Entrevista a Diego Amores. Emprendedor del Año	Radio Interview	https://play.cadenaser.com/audio/011RD01000000221231/
26/05/2019	INDEREN asistió a la reunión de lanzamiento del proyecto ValueWaste	Webpage news	https://inderen.es/es/inderen-reunion-lanzamiento-proyecto-valuewaste/
08/08/2019	NUUESTRO PROYECTO VALUEWASTE SE UNE AL CLÚSTER EUROPEO BIOREFINE	Webpage news	https://www.cetenma.es/nuestro-proyecto-valuewaste-se-une-al-cluster-europeo-biorefine/
08/08/2019	Biorefine Cluster Europe-Project section	Webpage news	https://www.biorefine.eu/valuewaste
10/09/2019	ValueWaste project presentation: fertilisers of the future	Webpage news	https://inderen.es/valuewaste-project-presentation-fertilisers-of-the-future/
18/09/2019	Presentación del proyecto ValueWaste: fertilizantes del futuro	Webpage news	https://inderen.es/es/presentacion-proyecto-valuewaste-fertilizantes-del-futuro/
10/10/2019	ValueWaste project presentation: insects protein a second life to urban waste	Webpage news	https://inderen.es/valuewaste-project-presentation-insects-protein-a-second-life-to-urban-waste/
17/11/2019	El reciclaje marrón llega a La Flota con 30 contenedores	Newspaper	https://www.laopiniondemurcia.es/murcia/2019/11/17/reciclaje-marron-llega-flota-30/1068802.html
21/11/2019	Ayuntamiento Murcia informa a las plazas de abastos sobre la instalación del quinto contenedor de recogida de orgánico	Newspaper	https://www.europapress.es/murcia/noticia-ayuntamiento-murcia-informa-plazas-abastos-instalacion-quinto-contenedor-recogida-organico-20191121114919.html
21/11/2019	Press release - Comercio y Limpieza Informan a las plazas de abastos sobre la instalación del quinto contenedor de recogida de orgánico	Press release	https://centromedios.murcia.es/PUBLICO/NotaPrensa/Default.aspx?pldPagina=25&pldNoticia=54260
01/12/2019	Valuewaste at the Solar Impulse Label Webpage	Webpage	https://solarimpulse.com/efficient-solutions/valuewaste
10/12/2019	Press release - Murcia, líder europeo en recogida selectiva con la implantación del quinto contenedor	Press release	https://centromedios.murcia.es/PUBLICO/NotaPrensa/Default.aspx?pldPagina=25&pldNoticia=54537
10/12/2019	La opinión- Los vecinos de La Flota podrán reciclar en el contenedor marrón en febrero	Newspaper	https://www.laopiniondemurcia.es/murcia/2019/12/10/flota-tendra-esperar-febrero-reciclar/1074873.html
10/12/2019	La Verdad-Murcia, líder europeo en recogida selectiva de basura orgánica con la implantación del quinto contenedor	Newspaper	https://www.laverdad.es/murcia/ciudad-murcia/murcia-implanta-quinto-20191210122744-nt.html

Date	Title	Type	Link
10/12/2019	Cadena Ser-Murcia pone en marcha una prueba piloto en recogida selectiva con la implantación del quinto contenedor	Webpage news	https://cadenaser.com/emisora/2019/12/10/radio_murcia/1575975143_164786.html
10/12/2019	ONDA REGIONAL El barrio de la Flota de Murcia será el primero en disponer de los nuevos contenedores marrones	Radio Interview/w ebpage news	https://www.orm.es/informativos/el-barrio-de-la-flota-de-murcia-sera-el-primero-en-disponer-de-los-nuevos-contenedores-marrones/
10/12/2019	COPE-La Flota será el barrio primero en incorporar el nuevo contenedor de tapa marrón	Radio Interview/w ebpage news	https://www.cope.es/emisoras/region-de-murcia/murcia-provincia/murcia/informativos-en-murcia/noticias/flota-sera-barrio-primero-incorporar-nuevo-contenedor-tapa-marron-20191210_570275
10/12/2019	EUROPA PRESS	Newspaper	https://fotos.europapress.es/fotonoticia/f2539373/
10/12/2019	“Obtener comida es clave porque seremos 10.000 millones de personas en 2050”	Webpage news	https://www.guiadeprensa.com/suplementos/anuario-diciembre-2019-el-mundo/cetenma/
12/12/2019	“Obtener comida es clave porque seremos 10.000 millones de personas en 2050”	Newspaper	https://www.guiadeprensa.com/suplementos/anuario-diciembre-2019-el-mundo/cetenma/
17/12/2019	Interview with Rebeca Pérez Ay. Murcia	Radio Interview	
18/12/2019	Interview with CETENMA	Radio Interview	
09/01/2020	Press release- Ayuntamiento de Comienza la fase de información de la campaña ‘Suma 1’ para dar a conocer a los vecinos de La Flota el nuevo contenedor marrón web page	Press release	https://centromedios.murcia.es/PUBLICO/NotaPrensa/Default.aspx?pldPagina=25&pldNoticia=54959
09/01/2020	La verdad-La Flota estrenará a finales de febrero el contenedor marrón de restos orgánicos	Newspaper	https://www.laverdad.es/murcia/ciudad-murcia/flota-estrenara-finales-20200109183545-nt.html
11/02/2020	EySMunicipales- Murcia pone en marcha la recogida selectiva de materia orgánica en el marco del proyecto ValueWaste	Newspaper	https://www.eysmunicipales.es/actualidad/murcia-pone-en-marcha-la-recogida-selectiva-de-materia-organica-en-el-marco-del-proyecto-valuewaste
21/02/2020	Las larvas murcianas que transforman miles de toneladas de residuos	Newspaper	https://murciaplaza.com/las-larvas-murcianas-que-transforman-miles-de-toneladas-de-residuos-en-un-ano
27/02/2020	La opinión- Los vecinos de La Flota estrenan este viernes el contenedor marrón	Newspaper	https://www.laopiniondemurcia.es/murcia/2020/02/27/vecinos-flota-estrenan-viernes-contenedor/1095011.html
27/02/2020	Press release- Ayuntamiento de Murcia - Los vecinos de La Flota estrenarán mañana viernes el nuevo servicio de recogida de residuos orgánicos	Press release	https://centromedios.murcia.es/PUBLICO/NotaPrensa/Default.aspx?pldPagina=25&pldNoticia=55663
27/02/2020	Murcia Plaza-Los vecinos de La Flota estrenan este viernes el contenedor marrón para residuos orgánicos	Newspaper	https://murciaplaza.com/los-vecinos-de-la-flota-estrenaran-este-viernes-el-contenedor-marron-para-residuos-organicos
27/02/2020	Los vecinos de La Flota estrenarán mañana viernes el nuevo servicio de recogida de residuos orgánicos	Webpage news	https://www.murcia.com/noticias/2020/02/27-los-vecinos-de-la-flota-estrenaran-manana-viernes-el-nuevo-servicio-de-recogida-de-residuos-organicos.asp
27/02/2020	GAIKER participa en el desarrollo de un sistema para valorizar los residuos orgánicos urbanos	Webpage news	http://www.gaiker.es/cas/noticias/desarrollo-de-un-sistema-para-valorizar-los-residuos-organicos-urbanos.aspx?id=3b1d44d6-7687-413b-9dca-9c5f226aac29&pagina=1&origen=noticias
28/02/2020	RETEMA-GAIKER participa en el desarrollo de un sistema para valorizar los residuos orgánicos urbanos	Webpage news	https://www.retema.es/noticia/gaiker-participa-en-el-desarrollo-de-un-sistema-para-valorizar-los-residuos-organicos-E6rfv

Date	Title	Type	Link
28/02/2020	Biorefine Cluster Europe Newsletter	Newsletter	File
02/03/2020	Residuos Profesionales- El Proyecto Valuewaste Investiga Una Solución Que Permita La Valorización Completa De Los Residuos Orgánicos	Webpage news	https://www.residuosprofesional.com/valuewaste-valorizacion-biorresiduos/
03/03/2020	IZARO- GAIKER participa en un proyecto para demostrar la viabilidad de un sistema para valorizar residuos orgánicos urbanos	Webpage news	https://www.izaro.com/gaiker-participa-en-un-proyecto-para-demostrar-la-viabilidad-de-un-sistema-para-valorizar-residuos-organicos-urbanos/c-1582879237/
08/03/2020	La verdad- Bares y restaurantes de Murcia se suman a los mercados en el uso del contenedor marrón	Newspaper	https://www.laverdad.es/murcia/ciudad-murcia/bares-restaurantes-suman-20200308005238-ntvo.html
16/03/2020	INDUSTRIAMBIENTE- Gaiker participa en el desarrollo de un sistema para valorizar los residuos orgánicos urbanos	Webpage news	https://www.industriambiente.com/noticias/20200316/gaiker-participa-desarrollo-sistema-valorizar-residuos-organicos-urbanos#.Xm8qTppKjIU
19/03/2020	Proyecto Valuewaste: residuos orgánicos como pieza clave de la economía circular	Newspaper	https://foromediambienteyostenibilidad.com/2020/03/19/gestion-de-los-residuos-organicos-pieza-clave-de-la-economia-circular/?fbclid=IwAR2AFI6AiP9-rDCwOV1C6fTLp- - iPeINS3NKE_AhOWWXUUGRgD2UXDKk0k
31/03/2020	Los vecinos de La Flota duplican el reciclaje diario de basura orgánica	Newspaper	https://www.laverdad.es/murcia/ciudad-murcia/vecinos-flota-duplican-20200331010842-ntvo.html
31/03/2020	La Verdad-Los vecinos de La Flota duplican el reciclaje diario de basura orgánica	Newspaper	https://www.laverdad.es/murcia/ciudad-murcia/vecinos-flota-duplican-20200331010842-ntvo.html
30/04/2020	Biorefine cluster newsletter	Newsletter	
18/05/2020	Ondacero - Special programme about the world recycling day - Ways of paving the way towards the implementation of Circular Economy- VALUEWASTE???	Radio Slot	https://www.ondacero.es/emisoras/murcia/murcia/audios-podcast/murcia-en-la-onda/mas-de-uno-murcia-180520_202005185ec27e65f0667a0001cd1f9d.html
15/05/2020	El biogás que produce energía, bacterias, proteínas y biofertilizantes	Magazine	energias-renovables.com/biogas-el-biogas-que-produce-energia-bacterias-proteinas-20200515
17/05/2020	Contenedor marrón: Un nuevo color para el reciclaje	Newspaper	https://www.laopiniondemurcia.es/comunidad/2020/05/17/contenedor-marron-nuevo-color-reciclaje/1114552.html
28/05/2020	Press Release- La campaña 'Murcia suma uno' del proyecto Valuewaste vuelve al barrio de La Flota	Newspaper	http://centromedios.murcia.es/PUBLICO/NotaPrensa/Default.aspx?pldNoticia=56424
30/06/2020	Newsletter QEPEC ¿Qué está pasando en CETENMA? Junio 2020	Newsletter	https://mailchi.mp/0e3d8c280458/qu-est-pasando-en-cetenma-2892706
28/07/2020	«La agricultura respetuosa ambientalmente es más rentable y duradera»	Newspaper	https://www.laverdad.es/agro/agricultura-respetuosa-ambientalmente-20200728001754-ntvo.html
28/07/2020	Special Issue "Agro". La Verdad (regional newspaper)	Magazine	https://www.laverdad.es/agro/agricultura-respetuosa-ambientalmente-20200728001754-ntvo.html ; https://cetenmaes.sharepoint.com/:f/r/actividad/com/Difusin/2020/Prensa%20y%20otros%202020/(07)%20La%20Verdad%20-%20Agro%20-%20Entrevista%20MSD%20(julio-2020)?csf=1&web=1&e=h1acYQ
06/08/2020	Newsletter QEPEC ¿Qué está pasando en CETENMA? Junio 2020	Newsletter	https://mailchi.mp/283b556a0239/qu-est-pasando-en-cetenma-3040314
26/08/2020	Press release - Murcia se suma a un proyecto europeo de gestión de los residuos orgánicos y de los procedentes de la construcción	Press release	https://centromedios.murcia.es/PUBLICO/NotaPrensa/Default.aspx?pldPagina=25&pldNoticia=57266#ad-image-0

Date	Title	Type	Link
30/08/2020	Murcia se alía con ciudades europeas para desarrollar cinco proyectos de economía circular	Newspaper	https://www.laverdad.es/murcia/ciudad-murcia/murcia-alia-ciudades-20200830003911-ntvo.html
04/09/2020	Press release - Murcia liderará un proyecto europeo sobre la puesta en valor de productos derivados del tratamiento de agua y residuos orgánicos urbanos	Press release	https://centromedios.murcia.es/PUBLICO/NotaPrensa/Default.aspx?pldPagina=25&pldNoticia=57341#ad-image-0
17/09/2020	Press release NURESYS-Pilot Unit shipment	Press release	C:\Users\INNOVARUM\INNOVARUM Dropbox\INNOVARUM Gestión Pytos\VALUEWASTE\Dissemination Valuewaste\D&C Actions\1E - Media Coverage
17/09/2020	NURESYS local TV for interview of pilot Murcia	TV interview	https://www.focus-wtv.be/video/nieuws-wtv-17-september
26/09/2020	Press release - La campaña informativa 'Murcia suma uno' vuelve al barrio de La Flota	Press release	https://centromedios.murcia.es/PUBLICO/NotaPrensa/Default.aspx?pldPagina=25&pldNoticia=57586#ad-image-0
30/09/2020	Newsletter QEPEC ¿Qué está pasando en CETENMA? Junio 2020	Newsletter	https://mailchi.mp/afd7885b02fa/qu-est-pasando-en-cetenma-5091978
01/10/2020	Murcia, ciudad pionera en economía circular	Magazine	https://www.eysmunicipales.es/revista/tercer-trimestre-mM
08/10/2020	Interview on Conexión Europa	Radio Interview	https://twitter.com/EuropeDirectRMu/status/1313427286851543045?s=20

6.2.4 EU Communication tools

6.2.4.1 Quality of the actions

The Valuwaste project has been represented and promoted through key EU Communication tools (table below), which include platforms like Cordis or EIP Agri. Moreover, the project uses in its social media channels recommended hashtags like #H2020 #EUCommission and mentions EU official accounts when relevant updates are released.

Picture 10: Valuwaste profile in Cordis

6.2.4.2 Numeric progress

Table 15: Valuwaste project pages and news in EU Communication routes

Websites	Title	Link
Cordis	ValueWaste: Unlocking new Value from urban bioWaste	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/218515/en
European Circular Economy Stakeholder Platform	ValueWaste: Unlocking new Value from urban bioWaste	https://circulareconomy.europa.eu/platform/en/good-practices/valuwaste-unlocking-new-value-urban-biowaste
EIP-agri	Unlocking new VALUE from urban bioWASTE	https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/en/find-connect/projects/unlocking-new-value-urban-biowaste
Horizon Results Platform (Pilot)	Towards the utilisation of biowaste as a resource: a review of EU Policy on biowaste management	<i>In progress</i>
Cordis news	17 EU organisations are working together to maximize the recovery of substances from organic waste generated in cities	https://cordis.europa.eu/article/id/422537-17-eu-organisations-are-working-together-to-maximize-the-recovery-of-substances-from-organic-

6.2.5 Events

6.2.5.1 Quality of the actions

Events covered a wide range of issues of interest to the promotion of the project like circular economy, bioeconomy, waste management, environment, the development of smart cities... and counted with the participation of the targeted audiences of the project. By M24, the project has been represented in 41 conferences, congresses, and workshops.

Picture 11: Valuewaste online presentation at the Smart Liveable Cities event in October 2020

Picture 12: presentation of Entomo Agroindustrial at the eWorkshop on Upcycled Proteins

Picture 13: Unibio reception on industrial biotechnology (Denmark) in December 2019

Circular Bioeconomy Days 2019

AI > ... > Conferences > Circular Bioeconomy Days 2019 > Posters

Posters (click on the picture to enlarge)

- > About Circular Bioeconomy Days
- > Registration
- > Programme and presentations
- > **Posters**
- >> Side events
- > Technical Tours
- > Organizing Committee
- >> About the venue
- > Contact

Picture 14: Valuewaste online poster presentation at the Circular Bioeconomy Days 2019

Due to the **COVID19 outbreak**, it was not possible to attend to events physically since mid-March (M17). From May 2020 onwards, activity of the project partners in online events and actions resumed. Currently, main activity in relation to events is online.

6.2.5.2 Numeric progress

Finally, Table 16 shows the conferences in which the ValueWaste project has participated:

Table 16: conferences with participation of the ValueWaste Project

Date	Title	Who	Type of participation	Link	No. attendees*
23/11/2018	II Workshop on the action plan for the climate and sustainable energy 2030	CETENMA	Round table. Presentation of the ValueWaste project, promotion with the Project roll-up.		15
21/02/2019	I Foro Internacional de Innovación, Sostenibilidad y Economía	MU FERROVIAL and Ayuntamiento de Murcia	Promoting ValueWaste to the attendees (individual talks). Distribution of informative brochures about ValueWaste and presentation of the Roll-up	http://www.regmurcia.com/eventos/42786	50
07/03/2019	II Jornada sectorial sobre Economía Circular 2019	CETENMA	Oral presentation on the ValueWaste project during the first circular economy sectorial forum in Murcia (Spain)	http://portal.molinadesegura.es/index.php?option=com_content&view=article&id=5729&Itemid=1393	30
11/03/2019	II Mesa de Trabajo del Plan de Acción para el Clima y la Energía Sostenible 20230 (PACES)	CETENMA	Round table and oral presentation of the ValueWaste project.	https://www.cetenma.es/mesa-de-trabajo-del-plan-de-accion-para-el-clima-y-la-energia-sostenible-de-alcantarilla/	15
14/03/2019	AEMA. JORNADA EMPRESA Y MEDIOAMBIENTE	MU FERROVIAL	Oral presentation of the ValueWaste project, online brochure distribution, informative brochures distribution onsite.	https://www.aema-rm.org/guia-prevencion-residuos/	20
27/03/2019	GREEN CITIES 2019 Malaga	ENTOMO	Oral presentation (“Valorización industrial de materia orgánica usando insectos”), description of the ValueWaste project	http://greencities.malaga.eu/opencms/export/sites/greencities/content/documentos/greencities/Programa-ELEVATOR-PITCH-.pdf	170 companies, 3,800 professionals

Date	Title	Who	Type of participation	Link	No. attendees*
04/04/2019	I JORNADA DE NUTRICIÓN NUTRIN	ENTOMO	Oral presentation of the project	http://www.integaonline.com/i-jornada-de-nutricion-nutrin/	30
12/04/2019	BBI JU INFO DAY 2019	FBCD	Promotion of the Valuwaste project and use of dissemination materials: roll up, brochure. Presentation of the project to attendees (individual talks).	https://www.bbi-europe.eu/events/bbi-ju-info-day-2019	300
26/04/2019	Course "Curso Gestor en Economía Circular"	CETENMA	Collaboration with training course on circular economy and oral presentation of the valuwaste project as an example.	https://www.cetenma.es/ya-puedes-inscribirte-al-curso-gratuito-que-te-formara-como-gestor-en-economia-circular/	25
08/05/2019	Advisory Board Scalibur Project (H2020)	CETENMA	Participation in EU Project Advisory Board and oral presentation of the Valuwaste Project	https://twitter.com/CETENMA/status/1126147096489361408	30
03/06/2019	World Circular economy forum	SAVONIA UNIVERTISTY	Promoting ValueWaste to the attendees (individual talks). Distribution of informative brochures about Valuwaste	https://www.sitra.fi/en/projects/world-circular-economy-forum-2019/	2,207 participants
06/06/2019	Event EU Green Week- Biowaste Management and Environmental Sustainability in EU - Think green every day!	EUBIA	Event organisation and oral presentation of the Valuwaste project. Round table.	https://www.eventbrite.com/e/eu-green-week-partner-event-biowaste-management-and-environmental-sustainability-in-eu-think-green-tickets-58575687458#	50
16/06/2019	ISPIM Conference	SAVONIA UNIVERTISTY	Valuwaste poster presentation	https://www.ispim-innovation-conference.com/	700 participants

Date	Title	Who	Type of participation	Link	No. attendees*
25/06/2019	“Circular Bioeconomy Days 2019”	FBCD and UNIBIO	Event organised by ABP. Oral presentation on the Valuwaste project by UNIBIO, Valuwaste online poster promotion.	https://conferences.au.dk/circularbioeconomydays2019/about-circular-bioeconomy-days/	50
27/08/2019	Food waste and Business opportunities	FBCD and UNIBIO	Valuwaste Oral Presentation - 13.00-13.20 Fra organisk affald til fødearengrediens ved Michael Jensen, Unibio/From organic waste to food ingredient by Michael Jensen, Unibio	https://danishfoodinnovation.dk/event/kick-off-forretningsgoerelse-af-foedevarespild/	56
06/09/2019	Food Festival	FBCD	Oral presentation on the “Food and lifestyle scene” and presentation of the Valuwaste project. Presentation of samples of Uniprotein® from ValueWaste partner Unibio	https://www.foodfestival.dk/en/	70 attendees to the presentation. More the 30,000 attendees to the festival
25/09/2019	Danish Bioeconomy Conference	FBCD	Roll-up and Uniprotein sample for exhibition.	https://inbiom.nemtilmeld.dk/images/descriptions/13164/Dansk Bioekonomi Konference 2019 - invitation og program 2019 - 29.08.19.pdf	60
03/10/2019	Stories of World Goals 2.0: Waste as a Resource	Kalundborg	Oral presentation of the project and on opportunities and challenges in waste.	https://nyteuropa.nemtilmeld.dk/82/	40
03/10/2019	Jornadas Económicas Locales en Murcia	Ayuntamiento de Murcia	Oral presentation of the project	https://www.um.es/observalocal/?p=33591	30
03/10/2019	Kick-Off meetng: project WausTUP!	INDEREN, CETENMA	Oral presentation of the project		30

Date	Title	Who	Type of participation	Link	No. attendees*
10/10/2019	I Foro Comprometidos con una Región de Murcia Sostenible	Ayuntamiento de Murcia	Oral presentation of the project and distribution of project brochures	http://7tvregiondemurcia.es/la7-reune-a-una-veintena-de-expertos-en-el-i-foro-comprometidos-con-una-region-de-murcia-sostenible/	100
25/10/2019	CLIMATHON MURCIA 2019	CETENMA, Ayuntamiento de Murcia, Ferrovial y Entomo	Climathon programme (Climate KIC) on citizens awareness. Oral presentation of the project and round tables to discuss ideas. Roll up and brochures promotion.	https://climathon.climate-kic.org/en/murcia	60
13/11/2019	European Conference: Boosting Innovation Through Standards ('Your Gateway To The Market')	UNE	Organiser and representant of ValueWaste	https://ec.europa.eu/research/index.cfm?pg=events&eventcode=4B5DCB77-99CE-FDE8-C09A0B5DD141A830	350
19/11/2019	Advisory Board Scalibur	CETENMA	Attendance & Oral presentation of the project		30
25/11/2019	Inauguration of new facilities of ENTOMO	ENTOMO, UNIBIO, CETENMA	Oral presentation of the project		55
02/12/2019	Resurbis Project-Closing meeting	INDEREN, CETENMA	Attendance & Oral presentation of the project		20
09/12/2019	Jornada paralela en #Murcia de la #COP25, organizada por @AEMArm	CETENMA	Oral presentation of the project	https://twitter.com/CETENMA/status/1204387356205355010	44
17/01/2020	Participation in Unibio reception.	FBCD and UNIBIO	Oral presentation of the project, presentation of roll-up and distribution of brochures, Roskilde		40

Date	Title	Who	Type of participation	Link	No. attendees*
03/02/2020	VW presented at "Green information meeting on 'Bio-Based Joint Undertakings for Industries, GUDP, MUDP and Grand Solutions"	FBCD	Oral presentation of the project	https://ufm.dk/aktuelt/arrangementer/2020/informationsmode-om-programmet-bio-based-industries-under-horizon-2020	35
27/02/2020	Waste Management in the Circular Economy	CENTENMA	Oral presentation of the project	https://euroacad.eu/ev/s2517/	78
06/05/2020	BIOENERGY AUSTRALIA WEBINAR SERIES	FBCD	Powerpoint presentation mentioning Valuwaste	https://www.bioenergyaustralia.org.au/events/65178/	45
06/05/2020	ICAW Webinar: Food Waste and the Circular	FBCD	Powerpoint presentation mentioning Valuwaste	https://www.compostingvermont.org/ica-w-denmark-webinar	53
28/05/2020	The eWorkshop on Upcycled proteins	Entomo, Innovarum	Participation in the eWrokshop on Upcycled proteins organised by Innovarum with a presentation of the Valuwaste project	https://www.eventbrite.com/e/the-eworkshop-on-upcycled-proteins-registration-101632369152#	125
04/06/2020	Jornada "De Residuos a Nuevos Productos"	CENTENMA	Guest Speaker - Delivered oral presentation on waste valorisation " <i>OBTENIENDO RECURSOS DE ALTO VALOR A PARTIR DE RESIDUOS: EXPERIENCIAS DESDE CETENMA</i> "	https://institudesostenibilidad.es/jornada-residuos-economia-circular/	190
10/06/2020	ISPIM innovation conference "Innovating in times of crisis"	SAVONIA UNIVERTISTY	VW Paper publication and presentation "Circular economy business models addressing social acceptance" and conference publication /Tuomo Eskelinen	https://www.ispim-virtual.com/	600
15/09/2020	ESEIA Summer school. Climate friendly bioenergy solutions. CE and waste management.	SAVONIA UNIVERTISTY	Valuwaste /Canada Hermosa site was presented as an example of climate friendly solution /Harri Auvinen	Moodle	20

Date	Title	Who	Type of participation	Link	No. attendees*
29/09/2020	World Circular Economy Forum	SAVONIA UNIVERTISTY	Tuomo Eskelinen presented Valuewaste as participant.	https://www.sitra.fi/en/news/wcef2020-in-toronto-next-fall/	600
01/10/2020	Course "Circular Economy management". Project Green Employment	CENTENMA	Collaboration with training course "Circular Economy management". Project Green Employment	https://cetenmaes.sharepoint.com/:f:/r/sites/GESTORECEMPRESAS/Documentos%20compartidos/Ejecuci%C3%B3n?csf=1&web=1&e=HgOm7B	33
01/10/2020	IFIB Conference	INNOVARUM	Valuewaste poster presentation	https://ifib-2020.b2match.io/page-1231	373
08/10/2020	Smart and Liveable Cities-City of LOTZ	MURCIA	Presentation of the state-of-the-art projects in EU.		32
16/10/2020	UNIMAR: UNIVERSIDAD INTERNACIONAL DEL MAR-CURSO AGENDA URBANA	MURCIA	Good practice of European Projects aligned with URBAN AGENDA 2030		40
19/10/2020	CAMPAIGN IN MARKET PLACES	MURCIA	Enhancement of the biowaste collection in market places. Oral presentation and deliver of VW dissemination materiales.		16
29/10/2020	KOM Hoop	CENTENMA	Oral and visual presentation of the Valuewaste project	https://twitter.com/hoop_eu/status/1321719815015452674	30

6.3 Planning for the second half of the project

6.3.1 Webpage

The webpage will continue doing periodic updates to assure that the content included showcases the current activity and actions carried out by the project. An important update foreseen for the second part of the project is the creation and design of new content for the “Communication Campaigns” tab, which currently only shows information for the Educational Campaign in Murcia (Task 10.2). In January 2021, the webpage will also be updated with information about the Awareness Campaigns in Murcia and Kalundborg.

Innovarum will also discuss with MU-FERROVIAL (responsible of Task 10.2), the Murcia City Council and the Kalundborg City Council (responsible partners of Task 10.3, Awareness Campaign in Murcia and Kalundborg) **options to digitally promote and consolidate the elements of the Awareness Campaigns (Task 10.3)**. This could include additional representation in the Valuwaste project web, or the maintenance of the webpage of the Educational Campaign in Murcia (Task 10.3, *Murcia Suma Uno*).

6.3.2 Social media

Social media will continue to maintain views and keep on increasing the followers’ base. To better measure progress, this plan proposes **new internal numeric targets** that the communication of the project will work to achieve:

Action	WP10 Target	Current situation	Updated internal target
Social media Twitter	300 followers	352	450
Social media LinkedIn	100 followers	298	400

In total, the project seeks to reach an audience of 850 people.

Likewise, Innovarum will look for new innovative ways to digitally communicate the project. An option that will be evaluated will be the recording of **interviews with each project partner** of the consortium through an online platform (potentially Zoom) in which partners **briefly talk about their work in the project so far and about any results that are available so far**. If partners can record themselves, videos of the workspaces could also be used.

6.3.3 Media coverages

The project still needs to continue with the promotion of the project in the **general media** (10 publications left) to reach its targets. Additionally, the project still needs to produce at least two more **press realises**:

1. **Announcement the start of the work pilot plant.** The pilot plant received the last pilot unit the 30 of October of 2020 (M24) and in November 2020 installation processes and tests were being carried out in Cañada Hermosa (Murcia).

The press release will be prepared by Innovarum, supervised by CETENMA, and delivered to all project partners for distribution when the **biowaste valorisation strategies** processes officially start. Potentially, at the beginning of December 2020.

2. Announcement of **the closing visit to the technical working lines in both municipalities.**

This action is part of Task 10.3, Awareness Campaigns in Murcia and Kalundborg.

6.3.4 Informative materials

6.3.4.1 External communication

The project still needs to produce 3 new **informative materials** to reach the targets set. To support Task 10.4, informative materials of the second half of the project will also cover updated results.

6.3.4.2 Internal communication

In order to make sure that project visual identity stands up to standards, during the second half of the project **all public deliverables will be reviewed by Innovarum (Communication partner) who will take care of the graphic design of the document.**

6.3.5 Participation in conferences and congresses

A list with events recommendations can be found in the Annexes of this document. Due to the COVID19, participation in offline onsite events has become complicated. Thus, online participation is expected in the coming months.

6.3.6 EU Communication routes

ValuEWaste uses the available EU Communication routes. In October 2020 it included a publication in the “Cordis News” section and from November onwards it will keep up uploading and updating there the situation of the project, especially when it comes to the promotion of results.

Besides, the project will keep on tagging and mention the EU social media channels. Finally, the project will get in contact with its Project Officer for the promotion of significant milestones or results.

6.3.7 Audio visual materials

During the final months of the project and when results are available for dissemination, a **new video with interviews with the project partners will be recorded**. An opportunity to record this video could potentially be the final event, when all project partners, relevant parties and projects will gather. This could be an option if the final event is not scheduled too late in the project schedule so there is time to disseminate the video.

Other options are (1) to record the video during the exchange visits between Murcia (Spain) and Kalundborg (Denmark), part of the Awareness Communication Campaign (Task 10.3); (2) or to do so remotely if there are enough results to communicate before.

6.3.8 Final event

At the end of the project, the “**final event**” will also be organised and carried out. Regarding the final event, the possible organisation of a common final action between ValuEWaste and Scalibur is also being considered.

6.3.9 Collaboration with friend projects

ValueWaste has been talking and engaging with friend projects: Scalibur and WaysTup!

Examples of collaboration actions include social media support and community engagement, and collaboration in future events. It is also being evaluated the organisation of a common workshop and the creation of a common mailing list or the publication of articles/posts in the project's respective webpages.

In future months, Valuwaste will start collaborating with the project Hoop⁷, which started in October 2020.

⁷ More information in Cordis: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101000836>

7 WP10 progress overview

The WP10 has followed the Dissemination & Communication Plan of the Valuwaste Project, which covers the Tasks, communication channels, targets and actions reviewed previously, that is, the D&C plan is representative of the WP10 as a whole. The next table summarises the progress of the D&C plan and, at the same time, of the WP10. The progress of the implementation of the actions is included in the right column (M24, October 2020).

Table 17: WP10 D&C Actions and progress (M1-M24)

1 - All target audiences		Final Target	M24 (Oct 2020)	Strategy
1 A	VALUEWASTE website & Blog	500 visits/month	650	Communication
		30 posts	30	Communication
1 B	Social Media	300 followers (twitter)	352	Communication
		100 followers (LinkedIn)	298	Communication
1 C	Audio-visual materials	2 videos	2	Communication
1 D	Other informative materials	15 informative materials	12	Communication
1 E	Media coverage	100 media coverages	90	Communication
1 F	Final event	80-100 attendees		Dissemination
1 G	EC Dissemination routes	Presence in 4 routes	5	Communication Dissemination
2 - General public			M24 (Oct 2020)	
2 A	Communication Campaign 1 – Murcia	Specific targets	In progress	Communication
2 B	Communication Campaign 2 – Murcia and Kalundborg	Specific targets	Preparation	Communication Dissemination
3 - Policy makers			M24 (Oct 2020)	
3 A	Meetings and interviews with policymakers	5 meetings	10	Communication Dissemination
3 B	Attendance to high level policy events	5 events	2	Dissemination
4 - Industry players			M24 (Oct 2020)	
4 A	Trade shows and fairs	15 events attended	7	Dissemination
5 - Academia				
5 A	Technical publications/ Papers	5	5	Dissemination
5 B	Workshops, conferences, and congresses	10 events	41	Communication Dissemination

In general, during the Reporting Period (November 2018-November 2020) progress of the communication and dissemination actions of the project is positive. 9 of the total 13 dissemination and communication actions established are completed (some of the targets have even been surpassed) and another 2 actions are 80% completed by Month 24 of the project (April 2020), when the 50% of the time of the project has passed.

Figure 4: Progress of the communication and dissemination actions in the D&C Plan 1

Figure 5: Progress of the communication and dissemination actions in the D&C Plan 2

7.1 The project communication and challenges

7.1.1 Project Communication through the first half of the project

The project communication has been active and has been producing quality actions since it started back in 2018. On the one hand, it has engaged with a wide variety of activities (events, publications, radio slots, tv shows, online workshops and activities...) of relevance to the project and to the promotion of innovative waste management systems

On the other, it has counted with active participation from all partners involved. Different partners have communicated the project through the tools and resources they had available, which all together have built a strong and efficient common communication channel to the project audiences.

7.1.2 Challenges: COVID19

One of the main challenges that the project is facing since February-March 2020 is the COVID19 pandemic and subsequent safety restrictions. Particularly, this has affected the second half of the Educational Campaign in Murcia (Task 10.2) and might affect the planning of the Awareness Campaigns in Murcia and Kalundborg (Task 10.3). The organisation of offline activities might be compromised, and even if it is possible to organise them impact might nevertheless suffer, specially throughout the first half of 2020.

In addition, the possibility to participate in events internationally and travel had to stop for some months due to restrictions. Now that the international event industry is adapting, more participation online options are appearing, however, format and global impact over the audience/participants is affected. As 2021 develops, the audiences will have time get used to this new type of communication channels and new innovative ways of participation might still appear.

8 Summary: future actions

Below there is a chart that shows the time execution of relevant actions mentioned in this deliverable for the coming months:

	Project month	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	42	43	44	45	46	47	48
Task	Action																							
10.2	Final months of the Educational Campaign in Murcia	█	█																					
10.3	Awareness Campaign in Murcia (Spain) and Kalundborg (Denmark)		█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█				
10.4	Trade shows and technical publication recommendations for the second half of the project. Identification of opportunities.	█	█																					
10.4	Online workshop targeted to industry stakeholders to promote project results										█	█												
10.4	Policy actions planned in D9.4		█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█			
10.5	Press release- The pilot plant starts working	█																						
10.5	New article in Cordis News about the pilot plant	█																						
10.5	Updated project presentation for online and offline use	█																						
10.5	Project webpage update with information from the Awareness Campaign in Murcia		█	█																				
10.5	Social media work	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█			
10.5	Final press release, project video with interviews, final event.																	█	█	█	█	█	█	█

8.1 General recommendations

Recommendations for all project partners facing the second plan of the project are:

1. Keep up active communication with Innovarum (communication partner) about the communication actions partners engage with. Whenever possible, a partner must **inform at least a week in advance of any relevant communication action** (event, media coverage...) that is planned.
2. To keep track of events during the COVID pandemic, project partners are encouraged to **take screenshots** of their participation in online events.
3. Until the COVID19 pandemic recedes, **participation in online activities is encouraged**.

8.2 Obligation to disseminate results

If new results come out, it will be important to pay attention to the obligation to disseminate results described on the Grant Agreement:

“(...) each beneficiary must — as soon as possible — ‘disseminate’ its results by disclosing them to the public by appropriate means (other than those resulting from protecting or exploiting the results), including in scientific publications (in any medium).”⁸

Project partners that intend to disseminate results must give **advance notice** to the Project Coordinator (CETENMA), the communication partner (Innovarum) as well as to all other project partners of **at least 45 days in advance**, together with sufficient information on the results it will disseminate. The **objection period will last 30 days** from the moment the notification is made, any partner can object to the dissemination of results during that time.

8.2.1 Open access to scientific publications

All project partners must ensure that all peer-reviewed scientific publications are open access. If a partner foresees that this can be issue or has questions, it shall contact the project coordinator (CETENMA) and the communication partner (Innovarum) to find a solution.

8.2.2 Obligation and right to use the EU emblem

Any result, or work produced by the ValueWaste project must display the EU emblem and include the following text:

“This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 818312”.

⁸ ARTICLE 29 — DISSEMINATION OF RESULTS — OPEN ACCESS — VISIBILITY OF EU FUNDING

9 Conclusions

The Valuwaste project is an active project who has actively engaged with communication actions since October 2018, when the project started. The first half of the project has been dedicated to communication of the structure, goals, and general work the project has been carrying out.

The second half of the project will keep on working on communication (through events, effective digital channels and new graphic materials and media coverages...) and, at the same time, will work to disseminate the results that Valuwaste starts to produce. Important events that will happen in 2021 and 2022 include end of the Educational Campaign in Murcia (Spain)-Task 10.2- and launching of the second communication campaign of the project, the Awareness Campaign in Murcia (Spain) and Kalundborg (Denmark)-Task 10.3..

Moreover, the second half of the project will work to boost the engagement with policy makers, the participation in trade shows and the publication of technical publications -Task 10.4. All these actions will be carried out in context still highly impacted by the COVID19, thus, it is important to mark that the planning included in this deliverable might need to be updated as the pandemic develops in order to adapt and assure impact and safety.

Finally, during the end of this second half of project development the final event of the project will take place.

10 Anexes

"This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 818312"

Estimado/a vecino/a:

Le informamos sobre las ubicaciones del nuevo contenedor marrón ubicados en el barrio de la Flota.

Este contenedor destinado a la recogida diferenciada de restos orgánicos forma parte de un importante proyecto europeo en pro de un medioambiente más cuidado y sostenible.

El proyecto VALUEWASTE propone un enfoque integrado para la valorización de la fracción orgánica de los residuos urbanos (biorresiduos), para obtener productos de alto valor añadido: proteínas para alimentación y biofertilizantes, entre otros.

El proyecto se desarrolla en dos ubicaciones europeas muy diferentes, Murcia (España) y Kalundborg (Dinamarca).. Los resultados del proyecto contribuirán al desarrollo de nuevos estándares y normativas, y constituirán información útil para la UE en términos de la protección medioambiental.

Queremos escuchar su opinión y hacerle entrega, además, de un práctico cubo doméstico, ideal para tirar los pequeños restos de materia orgánica que se van formando al cocinar. Gracias a su tamaño puede tenerlo siempre a la vista para usarlo en todo momento. Además, tiene un asa de transporte para facilitar su movilidad.

Si aún no lo tiene, ponemos a su disposición este canal de comunicación para poder conocer su valiosa opinión y obtener esta útil herramienta que facilitará la separación de sus residuos orgánicos: www.murciasumauno.es

Actualmente el nivel de participación de los vecinos en el barrio de la Flota es del 30 % por ello queremos incidir en la implicación de los vecinos para poder cumplir los objetivos que nos marca Europa. Sabemos que podemos contar con los vecinos de la Flota ya que actualmente sois el barrio más comprometido con el medioambiente.

" EI BARRIO DE LA FLOTA NECESITA MUCHO MÁS, NECESITA QUE MÁS VECINOS SE SUMEN AL RECICLAJE DE LA ORGÁNICA EN EL NUEVO CONTENEDOR MARRÓN "

Gracias por su colaboración.

Picture 15: Mailing Campaign from the Educational Campaign in Murcia in September 2020 to engage citizens in La Flota Neighbourhood

10.1 Draft table with events suggestions for all Valuwaste project partners

The table below contains events suggestions and descriptions for all project partners to review:

DATE	NO. DAYS	EVENT	TYPE OF EVENT	LOCATION	TOPIC	Note	Paper option	LINK
29/03/2021	3	World Bio Markets	Exhibition	Amsterdam (NL)	The go-to event and year-round private community for all your bio economy business development needs. Target: chemical, material and product industries			https://www.worldbiomarkets.com/
19/04/2021	4	Conama	Exhibition	Madrid (ES)	Spanish National Congress on Environment			http://www.conama2020.org/web/index.php
21/04/2021	2	Circular Materials Conference	Conference	Gothenborg (SE)	Industrial, scientific and commercial progress in circular use of materials.			https://www.circularmaterialscconference.se/
26/04/2021	3	EUBCE 2021	Exhibition	Online & Marseille (FR)	Global Biomass Innovation	E-Stands. Price: 1,500 to 2,500	Yes, usually November	https://www.eubce.com/

DATE	NO. DAYS	EVENT	TYPE OF EVENT	LOCATION	TOPIC	Note	Paper option	LINK
03/05/2021	4	eREC – Digital Recycling Expo and Conference for Circular Economy and Waste Management	Exhibition	Online	Virtual platform for the recycling industry that facilitates the national and international exchange between companies and customers.	E-Stands. Price: 2,000 to 3,800		https://erec.info/expo/
18/05/2021	2	ISWA: Waste-to-Resources 2021	Conference	Online	Waste-to-Resources is the world's leading conference on material-specific waste treatment. Usually held in in Hamburg, Germany, online for the Corona		Yes, usually November	https://www.iswa.org/nc/events-courses/calendar/eventdetail/show_detail/waste-to-resource-2021-call-for-papers-now-open/
08/06/2021	2	Sustainable Environmental Solutions Forum	Exhibition	Madrid (ES)	Forum of sustainable environmental solutions			https://www.ifema.es/en/fsms

DATE	NO. DAYS	EVENT	TYPE OF EVENT	LOCATION	TOPIC	Note	Paper option	LINK
08/06/2021	2	Foro de las ciudades	Exhibition	Madrid (ES)	Future of the cities of Spain, how they will evolve until 2030.	Sponsorship opportunities		https://www.ifema.es/foro-ciudades
28/09/2021	3	Expobiomasa	Trade show	Valladolid (ES)	Professional fair about biomass related projects			https://www.expobiomasa.com/
04/10/2021	4	eREC – Digital Recycling Expo and Conference for Circular Economy and Waste Management	Exhibition	Online	Virtual platform for the recycling industry that facilitates the national and international exchange between companies and customers.	E-Stands. Price: 2,000 to 3,800		https://eric.info/expo/
18/10/2021	2	19th Annual World Food Innovate Summit	Congress & Expo	Milan (IT)	Innovative ingredients, food industry			https://www.foodinnovateworld.com/
16/11/2021	2	Smart City Expo World Congress	Exhibition	Barcelona (ES)	Smart cities	Brokerage events		-
30/11/2021	2	Food Ingredients (Hi)	Trade show	Frankfurt (GE)	Innovation for the F&B industry			https://www.figlobal.com/hieurope/

DATE	NO. DAYS	EVENT	TYPE OF EVENT	LOCATION	TOPIC	Note	Paper option	LINK
Estimation: March 2021	3	BIOKET	Conference	Lille (FR)	Advanced and innovative biomass pretreatment; conversion and functionalization; extraction, separation and purification; process modelisation and analytical methods; design of bioprocesses, advanced fermentation.			https://bio-rocket-2020.b2match.io/page-4361
Estimation: November 2021		Circular Economy Summit			Sustainable development as a key issue for the future of industry			http://www.circulareconomysummit.com/en/home
Estimation: November 2021	3	Global Bioeconomy Summit	Exhibition		Bioeconomy projects	Video calls		https://gbs2020.net/
Estimation: November 2021	4	ECOMONDO	Trade show	Rimini (IT)	Leading event in Europe for the new models of circular economy		Yes, date not available yet	https://en.ecomondo.com/

DATE	NO. DAYS	EVENT	TYPE OF EVENT	LOCATION	TOPIC	Note	Paper option	LINK
Estimation: September 2021	A month	Greencities	Exhibition	Madrid (ES)	Reference meeting for all the agents involved in the construction of smart and sustainable cities in Spain.			https://greencities.fycma.com/?!ang=en
To be announced	5	EU Green Week 2020	Conference	Brussels (BE)	Nature and biodiversity	EU partner events		https://ec.europa.eu/info/events/eu-green-week-2020_en
To be announced	3	Symposium on urban mining and circular economy	Conference		Production, Consumption, Waste management, Innovation and investments. Sectors: Machinery and Equipment, Recycling, Urban development		Yes, date not available yet	https://www.urbanmining.it/
To be announced	3	Seeds & Chips Milano	Trade show	Milan (IT)	FOOD INNOVATION: Nextgen protein			https://seedsandchips.com/milano